
63. Catalogue validation

WHEN MAKING THE SUCCESSIVE Gaia data releases available to the world-wide scientific community, an important question is to what extent the star positions, distances, proper motions, photometry, and radial velocities can be ‘trusted’? What sort of independent validation can be made before publication? Have all instrumental (and relevant astrophysical) effects been correctly accounted for? Have there been any gross errors in some part of the enormous data processing chain?

In an analysis team comprising more than 400 people, with hundreds of thousands of lines of code written and maintained over many years and in many institutes, is the same numerical value of each critical parameter consistently used throughout?

FOR HIPPARCOS in the 1980s, the relatively modest data volume and discrete processing steps, combined with the interest of the various contributing countries, permitted a parallel reduction of the entire satellite data, by two independent data analysis teams: FAST, led by Jean Kovalevsky, and NDAC, led initially by Erik Høg and, after launch, by Lennart Lindegren.

But we could not wait to compare the final astrometric parameters to identify any possible algorithmic error. Instead, the processing being comprised of a number of discrete steps, enshrined in the 3-step method, allowed each to be verified, and if necessary corrected.

The two independently produced catalogues were then combined, into a unique agreed published catalogue, through a rigorous weighting procedure developed by Andrew Murray and Frédéric Arenou.

SUCH A PARALLEL reduction was out of the question for Gaia. The volume of data, its complexity, the manpower and computational resources required for even a single undertaking, ruled this out from the start.

Meanwhile, ensuring that every one of the more than 400 members of the Gaia Data Analysis and Processing Consortium would use the same values for the very broad range of natural physical and instrumental constants presented its own interesting challenge.

As examples, the (assumed) mass of the Sun, its quadrupole moment, the speed of light, and even the value of π (to 13 decimals!), are all crucial at accuracies of a microarcsec. So are many other constants of Nature. Also critical are the satellite spin rate, the CCD pixel sizes, the wavelength response of the G , B_p , and R_p systems, and hundreds of other instrumental constants, some of which may change as the mission progresses.

The solution was a centralised ‘parameter data base’ (Perryman et al., 2008), comprising many hundreds of relevant constants, expertly maintained by deputy project scientist Jos de Bruijne, along with structures for seamless inclusion into software codes.

ASTRONOMICAL TESTS that the Gaia data can be subject to are many. As a simple but forceful example, Data Release 2 has transformed the field of solar system occultations. Pre-Gaia, the predicted location of occultation passages on Earth could be wrong by thousands of km, with timings off by several hours, making observations a hit-or-miss affair. Today, with EDR3 positions and proper motions, predicted timings are typically good to within a few *seconds* (Essay #24).

Other tests can be more subtle. A powerful one, applied to Hipparcos by Lindegren (1995), examines the catalogue’s *negative* parallaxes. Given that a star’s parallax is a geometrical measure of its distance, it may seem alarming that there should be any! But the explanation is simple: any measured quantity has a measurement error associated with it, formalised as its ‘standard error’.

A star at very large distance will have a very small parallax, but the ubiquitous measurement errors may result in it ‘appearing’ to be negative. Indeed, it would be even more troubling if there were no negative parallaxes in the catalogue! And going further, the distribution of small and negative parallaxes results from the formal standard errors convolved with the true distribution of stellar distances. Equipped with a Galaxy model reflecting realistic star distances, the test proves to be a powerful one not only in verifying the parallax statistics, but also the fidelity of their estimated standard errors.

FOLLOWING ON from the sorts of validations for Gaia DR1 (Arenou et al., 2017), and DR2 (Arenou et al., 2018), an extensive battery of tests was made on the Gaia third data release, EDR3, by Fabricius et al. (2021). In the following, I will give an outline of some of them.

How complete is EDR3? Gaia has a practical limit for the number of simultaneous observations, dictated by the on-board memory, and telemetry capacity. Accordingly, when scanning close to the Galactic plane, and in particular across the low-extinction Baade’s Window, some of the fainter observations are not sent to ground. Tests show that incompleteness sets in at around $G \sim 20$, and at around $G \sim 19$ for the crowded Baade’s Window.

In globular clusters, calibrated via Hubble Space Telescope observations, completeness is around 60% for $G \sim 19$ mag even when the star density is $\sim 10^5$ stars per sq. deg. It is above 20% at $G \sim 17$ even at 10^7 per sq. deg. Not surprisingly, the inner and outer regions of globular clusters have very different levels of completeness.

FOR HIGH PROPER MOTION stars, EDR3 contains 633 sources with a proper motion above 1 arcsec yr^{-1} , and 2729 above $0.6 \text{ arcsec yr}^{-1}$. Such high proper motion stars are generally ‘nearby’, and tests have been made to verify that their parallaxes behave accordingly.

Some 8% of such high proper motion stars in the SIMBAD data base are still missing in EDR3, but it is expected that these will be picked up in later releases as the number of distinct observations increases, and as the astrometric solutions improved accordingly.

The limited sky coverage of EDR3 (with observations only between July 2014 and May 2017), combined with perturbations by close neighbours, explains the 1.5% of more than 500 million stars brighter than 19 mag without a full astrometric solution, i.e. these stars still lack an estimated parallax and proper motion.

The overall astrometric quality of EDR3 still shows certain limitations, as expected, including the residual imprints of the inhomogeneous sky coverage, again determined by the satellite scanning law. A number of large negative parallaxes can be traced to spurious solutions, again influenced by nearby stars on the sky, coupled with the still sub-optimal sky coverage.

PARALLAX ESTIMATES for distant quasars have been used to estimate the current large-scale variation of the parallax systematics, while independent catalogues of stars in the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds and the dwarf spheroidal galaxies of the Local Group, as well as catalogues of open clusters, have been used to examine the parallax zero point and associated systematics.

Meanwhile, a comparison of the proper motions from the Hipparcos Catalogue reveal a global rotation of the proper motion system well within the estimated accuracy of the Hipparcos reference frame ‘spin’.

OVERALL, comparisons with the Gaia Object Generator simulation tool, or ‘GOG’, show that the EDR3 data are broadly as expected from our knowledge of Galactic kinematics to very faint magnitudes, with the model itself possibly the cause of residual systematics.

As described in the context of the Hipparcos Catalogue validation outlined above, and in the framework of Gaia DR1 by Arenou et al. (2017, Section 6.2.1), the ‘true’ dispersion of the parallaxes was estimated using a deconvolution method applied to the negative tail of the parallax distribution. Again, this method provides insights into the underestimation of the standard errors, any residual systematics, and the present contamination due to non-single sources.

As confirmed by other tests, systematic terms have decreased compared to DR2, with remaining issues largely attributable to either shortcomings in calibration, or to perturbations by non-single stars.

Dependencies of the residual parallax bias on magnitude, colour, and ecliptic latitude of the source, at the levels of a few tens of microarcseconds, have been provisionally derived by Lindegren et al. (2021).

ANOTHER APPROACH to examining more subtle effects, such as the magnitude dependence of the parallax zero point, is through the use of resolved binary stars. For sufficiently long orbital periods, the proper motion of the two binary components should be similar. Potential common proper motion pairs were selected over the entire sky, being restricted to primaries up to $G < 15$ mag and to secondaries up to $G < 18$ mag. Other consistency tests were performed on the parallaxes of the two components of such wide physical binaries.

MANY VALIDATION TESTS were also made on the photometric data by Fabricius et al. (2021).

Most noticeably, artefacts in the colours due to the scan pattern in Gaia DR2, have largely disappeared in EDR3.

Their tests included internal checks of the photometric accuracy, comparisons with external catalogues, such as the Landolt standards, as well as the SDSS and Pan-STARRS1 standards, and comparisons of the $B_p - R_p$ colours with a Milky Way Galaxy model.

Photometry in crowded areas, such as globular clusters, still shows degraded quality, with the photometry in the inner regions shifted in both colour and magnitude.

